

Did Orlov buy the Orlov?

Among the few remaining large Mughal-cut diamonds, the most important is the Orlov diamond. Currently located in Russia, the popular story of how the gem was obtained by the Court of the Tsars differs significantly from its actual history. Anna Malecka investigates how the famous diamond really found its way to the imperial treasury.

The Russian emperors' gold sceptre is housed in the Moscow Kremlin, shown as part of the Diamond Fund collection. Created for Catherine II (1762–1796) by the two jewellers, Leopold Pfisterer and Ivan Leonovich, the item is made of gold and decorated with 197 diamonds with a total weight of 242.82 ct (Kuznetsova 2009).¹ Of the total weight, up to 189.62 ct falls to one gem: the Orlov, one of the largest Mughal-cut diamonds, which was

incorporated into the sceptre in 1774 (Rybakov 1975, Polynina 2012).

The gem is, in my view, identical to the one mentioned in the work of the famous gem merchant and traveller Jean Baptiste Tavernier (1605–1689), and known in Western literature as 'the Great Mughal's Diamond', or more frequently 'the Great Mughal'. In the seventeenth century, the emperors of Delhi kept the diamond in the treasury, from where it was looted by

Nadir Shah (r.1736-1747), the king of Iran, during his raid on India in 1739. The history of the gem after Nadir Shah's death is the subject of numerous stories. For the purposes of this article it is sufficient to explain that in 1766 the diamond was brought to Amsterdam from Isfahan, the former Persian capital, by Georgy Safras, an affluent Armenian gem merchant.

Contemporary authors writing on gems, including Lord Ian Balfour as the most prominent authority on historic diamonds, believed that the gem in question was purchased in Amsterdam by Russian prince Grigory Orlov (1734–1783), former favourite of Catherine the Great, who then gave it to the Empress as a gift to try and win back her graces. While accepting the most popular version of how the Empress obtained the diamond, Balfour nonetheless mentioned the existence of unspecified Russian documents, which were supposed to shed light on the process of the transaction (Balfour 2009, India 2014).

The earliest historical record of the Orlov is the last will of Safras, or, more precisely, Grigory Shafras Khodiminasov (son of Khwaja Minas), the name by which he was known in Russia. The author of this document, written in 1771 in Petersburg, asked his relatives (the Empress' banker and jeweller Ivan Lazarev (1735–1801) and his brother Akim Lazarev) to go to Amsterdam and take with them a 779 Dutch grain diamond (approximately 190 ct), which he had deposited in an Amsterdam bank in 1767.² The gem was the common property of Safras and Ivan Lazarev. It is known from Lazarev's testimony made in Petersburg in 1779, on account of the division of property between Safras' heirs that on 20 October 1772 he had given 125,000 rubles to Safras to pay off the remaining 50% of his share of the gem (Pyliayev, 2007).³ Probably both businessmen obtained the gem in Persia while working in close partnership, which was often the case with very expensive jewels (Huvhaniyan, 1379).

According to a very popular version of the story, Lazarev sold the diamond to Prince Orlov, who presented it to Catherine on her name-day on 24 November 1773.

The Orlov diamond, featured in the Imperial sceptre. © Elkan Wijnberg.

The gem was given in a decorative case in the form of a red egg (Potto, 2007).

This actually did take place. However, historical records show that in reality the former favourite of the Empress was only an actor in the great diamond performance, directed by Catherine herself.

The Empress was interested in buying the gem no later than in March 1773, when a model of the diamond was already in her court. Her correspondence with Adam Olsufev, the Empress' personal secretary, reveals that she paid for the diamond herself, taking 265,000 rubles out of the treasury between 1774 and 1780. The remaining 135,000 (of 400,000 — the total cost of the stone) had been paid earlier. In a letter dated 11 January 1774, addressed to Olsufev, the Empress insisted that her payments be made in secret and ordered him to pay in this way 75,000 rubles to Lazarev. The transfer was to take place "at such a moment that would coincide with the time Orlov had contracted to purchase the gem from the jeweller prior to giving it to her as a gift". And so it appears that even the court jeweller was unaware of the Empress' schemes. It is all the more probable since he entered into a formal agreement of purchasing the diamond with the count.

It was therefore not Orlov who bought the gem, but Catherine herself. Why then did she take so much care to create the impression in the court that the diamond was purchased by Orlov? The key to answering the question is the date the diamond was purchased. In 1773, Russia was struggling with two military undertakings: the war against Turkey and Pugachev's rebellion. In these circumstances, buying such a costly and excessive gem would definitely be treated by the Petersburg court as a controversial idea, to say the least (Baziiants, 1982).

It is known that the Empress was an enthusiast and collector of diamonds. Was the reason for her decision to purchase this stone tied only to this? Catherine was probably aware that the specimen offered to her is larger than other stones found in the possession of contemporary European rulers, and owning this exceptional stone

Oil on canvas portrait of Empress Catherine the Great by Russian painter Fyodor Rokotov, 1763.

would give her distinction among these rulers. Could this have been the reason for Empress Catherine's decision to acquire that diamond?

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Notes

1. In Edward Twining's classic book *A History of the Crown Jewels of Europe*, Twining claims that the sceptre was designed by a man named Troitinski, who is in turn called Troitnoki by Lord Balfour (Twining, 1960; Balfour 2009). Russian records of Catherine's sceptre do not mention any person by this name. It is likely that both writers misspelled the name of a man called Troinitski, who was not actually a jeweller but a director at the Hermitage Museum from 1918 to

1927, and was the author of several works on historic Russian diamonds.

2. The Lazarevs were an Armenian family residing in Isfahan, Iran, since the seventeenth century, where they were involved in the gem and jewellery business. One of them, Lazar, was to become a jeweller for the Persian Shah Abbas II (1642–1666). During Nadir Shah's reign, when Armenians were being persecuted, the father of the future Empress' jeweller, Lazar Lazarian, who was also in the gem trade, emigrated to Russia (SAOOIA, 1838; Kuznetsova, 2009).
3. Another important gem which came to Russia through Safras is the 46.92 ct diamond from the imperial orb. This stone was bought by a Russo-Armenian prince, Ivan Abamelek, who later traded it with Tsar Paul I for land (Baziiants, 1982; Kuznetsova 2009).

Gem and Jewellery History

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